

Should we test and treat the fever triggers or the fever that creates the immune system against the fever triggers?

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Abstract

Fever is the body's defense mechanism against the triggers of fever. Fever triggers are not substances that create the immune system for fever and its functions. These substances reduce heat, increase inflammation, and reduce blood flow.

The causes of fever triggers, the triggers of fever, and the substances produced by the immune system fight against the triggers of fever, their functions are not the same, and they are opposite to each other.

Fever triggers caused by external factors are always harmful to the body, but a fever that builds immunity against it is always beneficial to the body.

The current definition, diagnosis, and treatment of fever do not mention the substances that trigger fever.

Today's fever treatment destroys the substances that create immunity against the triggers of fever and increase the triggers of fever. It is not a treatment according to any scientific law in the world today, but a murder attempt. Fever should be checked and treated, not for the fever, but for its triggers.

Keywords: Fever triggers; Inflammation; Immune system; Prostaglandins; Oxygen consumption

1. Introduction

Fever is the body's defense mechanism against the stimulus (inflammation) of fever¹.

Fever triggers are not substances that create the immune system for fever and its functions. Any substance that is cooling or reducing temperature (antipyretic) is a fever stimulant because it increases inflammation and reduces blood flow. Antipyretics are the only substances needed to induce fever in any organism. By using antipyretics in anyone, anyone can reduce the body's heat energy and cause inflammation and fever within a few hours.

1.1. What are the triggers of fever? What are they?

Fever triggers are substances and their actions that trigger the immune system to induce fever. These substances reduce heat, increase inflammation, and reduce blood flow.

Fever triggers include water below body temperature, soft drinks, ice cream, weather, medications including paracetamol² that reduce body heat and increase inflammation, some vaccines, toxins, etc.

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Decreased blood flow due to severe inflammation is the sole trigger for fever. Any substance that is cooling or reducing temperature (antipyretic) is a fever stimulant because it increases inflammation and reduces blood flow. Antipyretics are the only substances needed to induce fever in any organism. By using antipyretics in anyone, anyone can reduce the body's heat energy and cause inflammation and fever within a few hours.

The causes of fever triggers, the triggers of fever, and the substances produced by the immune system fight against the triggers of fever, their functions are not the same, and they are opposite to each other.

Fever triggers caused by external factors are always harmful to the body, but a fever that builds immunity against it is always beneficial to the body.

While substances that stimulate fever reduce heat, increase inflammation, and decrease blood flow, substances that create an immune response in fever increase heat, reduce inflammation, and increase blood flow.

1.2. What are the substances and actions that the immune system takes to increase blood flow against fever triggers?

It constricts blood vessels under the skin to prevent heat loss from the body, reduces hunger and thirst, prevents sweating and defecation, creates an aversion to cold objects, and produces chemicals needed to prevent heat loss from the body.

Our immune system produces substances, including prostaglandins, that cause heat to increase body temperature, increase oxygen consumption, like hot objects, and produce chemicals necessary to increase body temperature.

Before a fever occurs, when the body's heat energy decreases, its symptoms, actions, signs, signals, and messages occur. Similarly, when the inflammation that stimulates the fever increases, its symptoms, actions, signs, signals, and messages occur. As a result, when blood flow decreases, its symptoms, actions, signs, signals, and messages occur. When the immune system creates a fever to fight it, its symptoms, actions, signs, signals, and messages also occur.

2. Symptoms of fever or symptoms of fever triggers.

Body aches, bitterness in the mouth, fatigue of mind and body, loss of appetite, reduced motion, indigestion, aversion to cold things, and internal and external discomfort are believed to be the symptoms of fever. These are not actually symptoms of a fever. These are symptoms of decreased blood flow and heat loss as a result of increased inflammation, which is a symptom of fever triggers. These symptoms can also be seen in hypothermia, where the temperature drops.

Symptoms of hyperthermia include likeness towards cold items like drinking cold water, feeling discomfort while using a blanket, feeling hot, etc.

Signs of fever include increased prostaglandins (PGE2), increased TNF alpha, decreased firing rate of heat-sensing W neurons, increased firing rate of cold-sensing C neurons, constriction of blood vessels under the skin, increased blood flow to vital organs, decreased blood flow to less vital organs, and heat production.

Most of these signs are also seen in hypothermia. These are not signs of the fever trigger. They are signs of the fever producing an immune response against the fever trigger.

Signs of fever triggers include increased inflammation and decreased blood flow. C-reactive protein, which is produced by the liver, is found in higher levels in the blood in people with high fever triggers.

When you have a fever, the most important organs increase in function and the least important organs decrease in function. This is not because of an increase in temperature. It is because of a decrease in essential blood circulation. It is like an inverter that is used to operate most essential lights and machines in emergencies caused by a power outage. When there is a decrease in essential blood circulation, the body increases the function of the most important organs such as the brain, heart, kidneys, and liver.

3. The current definition of fever does not mention any fever-triggering substances.

Therefore, fever triggers are not included in fever testing or treatment. It is wrong to say that fever testing and treatment are being done.

What needs to be examined and treated is not the fever, which only benefits the body by generating an immune response against the fever triggers, but the triggers of the fever.

The levels of fever-triggering substances in the body that are harmful to the body should be checked, and treatment should be aimed at reducing the levels of these substances.

People with weakened immune systems have high levels of inflammation, which triggers fever. They do not have the heat of fever because their immune system is unable to produce the heat of fever (prostaglandin E2).

According to any scientific law in the world today, there should be no test or treatment to eliminate fever that creates immunity against the triggers of fever.

Similarly, according to any scientific law in the world today, a symptom is caused by a disease, and a fever that creates immunity against the disease or triggers of fever should not be called a symptom.

What is the reason why today's fever treatment is a murderous treatment?

Rather than identifying and eliminating the triggers of fever, today's definition, testing, and treatment focus on identifying and eliminating the substances the immune system produces to fight against the triggers of fever.

In addition, today fever is diagnosed and treated as hyperthermia, the opposite of fever. Hyperthermia cannot be caused by substances that cause fever. Similarly, fever cannot be caused by substances that cause hyperthermia. The symptoms and actions of hyperthermia and fever are contradictory.

The stimuli that trigger the immune system to produce a fever and the substances that the immune system produces when a fever occurs are not the same, but their functions are opposite to each other.

Eliminating fever, which creates immunity against fever stimuli, and treating fever as hyperthermia will increase morbidity and mortality. It is not a treatment according to any scientific law in the world today, but a murder attempt.

People who don't know what causes fever, mistakenly believing that it is a symptom of some disease, and mistakenly believing that fever is dangerous, commit all these atrocities against fever.

Whatever those who misunderstand about fever do, that is what is done in today's fever treatment.

3.1. Can fever be cured without treatment?

It is not the fever that creates immunity that needs to be cured. It is the triggers of the fever that needs to be eliminated. The triggers of fever caused by external causes is always harmful to the body, while the fever that builds up the immune system against it is always beneficial to the body.

There is no need to treat fever, which is caused by the immune system increasing blood flow to fight off the fever's triggers. A disease that would have healed itself due to the activity of the immune system becomes serious and fatal due to unscientific treatment. It is enough not to harm the immune system, even if it does not help it.

The immune system, which works to eliminate the triggers of fever, can be supported by using warming materials and helping to prevent heat loss.

The only solution against fever triggers is to increase blood flow and reduce inflammation. This is an immutable scientific fact (It is incorrect to say that fever is the cure. It is perfectly correct to say that the only remedy is to increase blood flow and reduce inflammation).

The body temperature of the brooding hen increases to provide the required temperature for the egg and to increase the essential blood circulation in the body.

The brooding hen does not eat anything. The increased temperature is its food. It helps to convert fat into energy. Similarly, our immune system generates fever to increase the body's essential blood circulation.

3.2. Can the cause of the fever trigger or the cause of the disease be eliminated?

In most cases, the cause of the fever trigger or the underlying cause of the disease cannot be eliminated. Excessive swelling caused by cooling the body with sterile cold water, swelling caused by eating too much ice cream, swelling caused by rain, and swelling caused by fear, inflammation after a dog bite are all causes of fever induction, which have occurred in the past, and the cause of fever induction cannot be eliminated.

No matter what tests are done, the cause of the above swelling cannot be found through tests.

In such cases, there is no point in finding the cause of the inflammation that is stimulating the fever. This is because, in the above cases, treatment cannot be carried out at the source of the fever triggers.

The test is supposed to find out how many fever triggers are in the body and what they are.

Today, however, a diagnosis is not done to determine the triggers of fever. The test is to determine the disease and its cause. Since fever is not a disease or a cause of disease, a diagnosis of fever is not necessary.

3.3. Will the disease or fever go away if the cause of the trigger of the fever or the cause of the disease is eliminated?

If the cause of the disease is eliminated, the disease (problems and harms) caused by the cause of the disease will not change. Most diseases are caused by viruses. Today, even in diseases caused by viruses, antibiotics are prescribed to eliminate secondary infections. Antibiotics are given to kill bacteria when a fever is suspected to be caused by bacteria. Less than one percent contains bad bacteria that make people sick. It is estimated that a healthy digestive system (gut) contains approximately 85% good bacteria and 15% bad bacteria. Killing bacteria or viruses does not change the problems and harm they cause. It does not change the inflammation and poor blood circulation caused by the disease.

Even though the virus that causes the disease has disappeared, those infected with Chikungunya and those infected with the Coronavirus still experience the problems and harms that occurred back then.

If worms eat the leaves and branches of a plant, the branches will dry up. You can kill the worm that ate the plant. If you kill the worm, the worm-eaten, dried branch will not sprout. We can kill the tiger that scared us. Killing the tiger will not change the fear, the unconsciousness, and the fever caused by the fear.

3.4. Are viruses, bacteria, and fungi the cause of fever or the cause of disease?

Medical textbooks state that the causes of fever are viruses, bacteria, fungi, and protozoa. None of these are needed to cause a fever. Anyone can induce a fever by using sterile cold water to reduce body heat and increase inflammation. Antipyretic substances alone are sufficient to induce fever. Consuming large amounts of sterile cold water or ice cream can cause fever. This is the cause of fever if we stay wet for a long time.

Any substance that is cooling or reducing temperature (antipyretic) is a fever stimulant because it increases inflammation and reduces blood flow.

Viruses, bacteria, fungi, and protozoa cause disease, not fever. Those who do not know the real cause of fever say that viruses and bacteria are the root cause of fever and that treatment should be given for it.

It is not necessary to cure the disease to cure the fever. You don't need to change the disease or cause of the disease to eliminate the fever. Reducing inflammation and increasing blood flow will prevent the immune system from causing the fever.

Cancer patients rarely have a fever. Cancer does not go away if the fever goes away. If the cause of the disease is eliminated, the disease (problems and harms) caused by the cause of the disease will not change.

Those who do not know the true cause of fever say that viruses and bacteria are the underlying cause of fever and should be treated for that reason.

No bacteria or virus is needed to cause fever.

Fever is not a part of the disease, it is a part of the self-defense mechanism of the body, and it is an adaptation and a result of Thermogenesis.

3.5. Can a thermometer be used to test for fever triggers?

No. The thermometer measures the heat produced by the immune system against fever triggers. The CRP test and the ESR test are useful for measuring fever triggers.

3.6. How to differentiate between hyperthermia and fever in conscious patients

Suppose you feel uncomfortable in cold, cold water or contact with cold objects and prefer warm or hot objects. If so, this is a symptom that the body's defense system (fever) is reducing inflammation and increasing blood flow when inflammation reduces blood flow. Conversely, it is a symptom of hyperthermia if you feel an aversion to hot objects and prefer cold objects.

3.7. What is the treatment for fever triggers?

The treatment of fever triggers is to reduce fever triggers. It is essential to avoid situations that cause fever triggers. These are exposure to cold objects, weather, and situations that are colder than body temperature. For example, prolonged exposure to rain, cold weather, cold foods,...

4. A technique that reduces fever temperature within 20 minutes by stopping excess heat production by the immune system

Heat should be supplied from outside the body to the body and inside the body.

Hot bathtubs, steam baths, sauna baths, hair dryers, thermal heat pads, hot water bags, hot sand, and anything else that gives heat can be used to provide heat from outside the body to the body. Each patient should be given a tolerable and preferred temperature.

Warm water, tea, hot porridge, and easily digestible hot food can be used according to hunger and thirst to heat the body from outside to inside. Drink hot water boiled with pepper and ginger. Gargle your throat with warm salt water at a tolerable temperature. Those who apply heat using a hair dryer, thermal heat pad, hot water bag, and sand should apply heat several times until the body is comfortable and sweaty.

When the body sweats when it is heated or it is covered with blankets, or it is steamed, the water reduces the temperature, so the sweaty water should be wiped off with a dry cloth. When the patient feels discomfort, lying in hot water, heating, steaming, and steam baths should be stopped. These should be done only when the patient likes it.

Mechanisms should be made to prevent body heat from escaping. One should sit and lie down in a warm place where the temperature is above the fever temperature. Covering with wool or an insulated dress will reduce the rate of body heat loss.

5. A way to get heat from outside the body to every part of the body

Immerse yourself in warm water (tolerable) in a bathtub heated up to 107.60F from under the nose to full-foot immersion. The fever temperature will also drop faster because all parts of the body are warmed up evenly, blood flow increases and the immune system stops producing more heat.

People who don't know what is causing the heat and discomfort of the fever say if you take the medicine, the fever will go away within 7 days or a week.

Those who do not know what a fever is, distinguish between fever based on the number of days the temperature lasts.

5.1. Will paracetamol and water help eliminate the fever triggers?

Paracetamol and water never eliminate the triggers of fever, but they can eliminate the substances that increase the immune response against the triggers of fever, thereby stimulating the triggers of fever.

If the amount of substances produced for fever in response to fever triggers is reduced, blood flow is likely to decrease, as the ability to adhere to blood vessels increases proportionally with each degree decrease in temperature.

At this stage, we are unaware of this because our immune system generates heat through shivering muscles, reduces blood flow to non-vital organs, and constricts blood vessels under the skin to increase blood flow. It has been proven years ago that using heat-reducing materials can increase inflammation, cause infection, and even cause death. Antipyretics like paracetamol have been proven worldwide to cause inflammation and infection.

Medical books say that *"Our understanding of the neural basis of thermoregulation and fever is still rudimentary"*³ *"paracetamol may cause fever, neutropenia, thrombocytopenia, nephropathy, and skin reactions"*³, *Antipyretics cause prolonged infection, which increases death*⁴.

Study shows that *in hospitalized adults with fever, fever therapy does not reduce mortality or serious adverse event*⁵.

5.2. What happens if you provide heat to the body against the triggers of fever?

Heat increases blood flow by expanding blood vessels. As the temperature rises, the free flow time of blood, erythrocytes, and plasma decreases.

Studies have shown that temperatures at the same temperature as a fever (38 to 42 degrees Celsius) can increase blood flow by 27% to 144%⁶.

Studies have shown that when the temperature increased from 36.5° to 39.5°C, the blood-free flow time decreased by 10.38%, the erythrocyte-freeflow time decreased by 9.92%, and the plasma-free flow time decreased by 4.99%. This increases the speed of blood flow. During this time, the inflammation that triggers fever will decrease. The firing rate of w neurons will increase, and the firing rate of c neurons will decrease. The production of prostaglandins will decrease.

Since there is no fundamental difference between the temperature of a fever and the heat we provide, the temperature of a fever increases blood flow. Increased blood flow can help relax tight muscles, restore movement, and reduce pain. Temperature below 107.6 °F degrees never causes any harm to our body.

During summer, in some parts of India atmospheric temperature is more than 120°F degrees. A sauna's temperature ranges from 160 to 200 degrees Fahrenheit. In a steam bath, a person sits for 15 to 25 minutes.

While taking a normal Steam bath the temperature inside the box is more than 50 degrees centigrade, Physiotherapy Treatment temperature is between 52.5 °C to 54.4 °C.

All of this can be recreated using materials that reduce heat again. All this can be verified using existing tools.

Physicians say that for every degree of temperature above 37 degrees, 13% more oxygen is needed, and the body uses more energy than when all the organs are working normally, if the temperature of the fever is reduced, the need for oxygen will decrease, and it is good for the body. There is no scientific evidence for this belief. But the fact is against this belief.

Conductive topical heat treatment of the knees of healthy subjects increased popliteal artery blood flow by 29%, 94%, and 200% after 35 minutes of treatment with heating pad temperatures of 38 °C, 40 °C, and 43 °C, respectively⁷.

A 1°C increase in tissue temperature is associated with a 10% to 15% increase in local tissue metabolism. Increased blood flow facilitates tissue healing by supplying protein, nutrients, and oxygen at the site of injury.

Without knowing the purpose of fever temperature and examining what the body does with this heat energy, current fever testing and treatment is based on the belief that fever is a temperature above 100.4 °F and that temperature is harmful to the brain and body. There is no scientific evidence for this belief. But the truth is against this belief.

There is not even one percent evidence that heat-producing substances such as prostaglandins produced by the immune system are the cause triggers of fever.

There is 100 percent evidence that fever triggers are the triggers of fever.

To reduce morbidity and mortality, it is essential to ban current fever treatments that eliminate fever temperature and other substances that enhance immunity against fever triggers.

While pointing out the disadvantages of existing fever treatments, some who are unaware of the triggers of fever and what is needed for fever are now making a new argument that the correct treatment is to treat the cause of fever rather than just treat the fever. But they treat fever in a way that contradicts this argument.

Most fever protocols state that if the fever temperature is above 41°C, regardless of the cause, it should be immersed in ice water.

Giving paracetamol, which blocks the heat-causing substance prostaglandin E2, against the triggers of fever, and treating with water to reduce the temperature is not a treatment against the cause of the disease. This proves that they do not have a clear understanding of the fever treatment they are doing.

While studies report that there is no evidence that treating fever reduces illness, there are also studies that show that many deaths are caused by fever triggers.

5.3. How can prove that today's fever treatment destroys the substances that create immunity against the triggers of fever and increase the triggers of fever?

We can recreate the fever and cure it again. In modern science, a key criterion for deciding whether something is true it must be reproducible.

When antipyretics are given to reduce someone's body temperature, blood flow is reduced and fever occurs. Heat application reduces inflammation and increases blood flow, thereby lowering the fever temperature. Again, with the cold water, the body can reproduce the temperature of the fever.

When the fever recreates, it is not just the heat of the fever that occurs, but the rise in temperature that is just one of many factors, the fever is not a symptom, the fever has symptoms, signs signals, actions, and the patient does not die of a rise in temperature... anyone can test for themselves.

If we ask any type of question related to fever by assuming that today's fever treatment destroys the substances that create immunity against the triggers of fever and increase the triggers of fever we will get a clear answer.

If we do any type of treatment by assuming that the temperature of fever is to increase essential blood circulation, the body will accept, but at the same time body will resist whatever treatment to decrease blood circulation.

In addition, there is no need for further evidence to prove that current fever treatments destroy the substances that create immunity against fever triggers and increase fever triggers.

Whatever happens to a brooding hen and its egg if sponged with water, the same happens to a fever patient if the temperature is decreased by sponging. The same thing happens in *Thalaikku Oothal*[®]. ("Thalaikkuoothal" is a ritual in Tamil Nadu that involves pouring large amounts of water on the head and drinking cold coconut water to induce fever, fits, and death. Drinking chilled tender coconut water helps reduce body heat that causes fever, fits, and death. Drinking cold water during fever helps reduce body heat that causes fever, fits, and death).

The basic elements necessary for a scientific treatment are not provided in fever treatment.

It is proven that fever medicines are more dangerous than the disease, and fever treatments are more dangerous than fever triggers.

Any kind of question asked in various directions about today's fever treatment is that it destroys the substances that create immunity against the triggers of fever and increases the triggers of fever, and the answer is that it will increase inflammation and reduce blood circulation.

If what we say about a subject is incomplete or unscientific, there will be many questions about it and somewhere there will be a gap as if it is not met.

6. The importance of the findings of today's fever treatment is that it destroys the substances that create immunity against the triggers of fever and increases the triggers of fever

- Immediate relief from fever triggers and body pain.
- Life-saving discovery.
- A single magic answer to every fever-related question.
- If medicines and tests are prepared according to the purpose of the temperature of fever and fever triggers any country can guide the world in the cure for fever triggers.

7. Conclusion

The conservative definition, diagnosis, and treatment of fever do not mention the substances that trigger fever. Today's fever treatment destroys the substances that create immunity against the triggers of fever and increases the triggers of fever. In addition, today fever is diagnosed and treated as hyperthermia, the opposite of fever.

Fever should be checked and treated, not for the fever, but for its triggers. The only solution against fever triggers is to increase blood flow and reduce inflammation. This is an immutable scientific fact.

It helps to heal inflammation and disease quickly and preserve health.

There is only one way to reduce the mortality rate, and that is to ban conservative fever treatment, and there is no other way.

Conservative fever definition, diagnosis, and treatment should be revised according to the sensible and discreet action of the immune system.

Compliance with ethical standards

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I acknowledged to patients, authors of reference, etc.

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